

EdTech Hub

Clear evidence, better decisions, more learning.

the
Education
Commission

#SaveOurFuture Background Paper

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**#SaveOurFuture:
EdTech and the COVID-19
Response**

#SaveOurFuture

- Written to provide background information to assist in drafting the Save Our Future white paper Averting an Education Catastrophe for the World's Children
- #SaveOurFuture campaign addresses Education In Crisis, especially in the stark reality of a post-COVID-19 world
- Focuses on serving the most marginalized and identifying priority areas and 'quick wins' in the next 6-24 months
- With EdTech marred by a history of failed 'silver bullet' interventions, how might we harness EdTech most effectively to address the root causes of the learning crisis?

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The Working Group

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The Background Paper

The COVID-19 pandemic has exacerbated the learning crisis: over 1.1 billion learners have lost access to their classrooms

Immediate response to crisis involves a wide variety of tech, inc., radio & TV, mobile phones

Evidence from low-income countries indicates that few children are using EdTech to learn during the current pandemic

EdTech carries potential polarizing effect: exacerbate or reduce inequity

Research on EdTech has been limited and shows a mixed picture

EdTech can be leveraged for systems recovery and resilience (systems approach to tech)

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The Recommendations

What to invest in [to reach the poorest]?

Education Data

Collect appropriate,
usable data.
Get it used for
decision making.

Teacher professional development

Follow best evidence.
Don't fragment.
Share resources.

Radio, print, TV

Share resources.
Accessibility.
Open licensing,
editable.

What not to invest in [to reach the poorest]?

Online learning /
platforms /
e-content

Use radio, print, TV
instead.

Video lessons

Use Ubongo Kids /
Sesame St. / Digital
Storytime instead.

Internet /
broadband

Minimal connectivity
for WA/Telegram etc
is helpful. But *that's*
all folks...

Disclaimer

Books alone don't do it — but they are a key ingredient (Piper et al., 2018).

Books - worked example

Cost of **developing** a
1 grade / 1 subject set
of student materials

Plus printing costs.

Cost of **buying** a 1
grade / 1 subject set
of student materials

Plus printing costs.

Cost of **buying** a 1
grade / 1 subject set
of student materials
for **four** countries.
Plus printing costs.

What to
invest in?

Low-tech

Ask 1. Collect and use the right education data

Strengthen education systems and workforce management with digital approaches to collect and analyse school- and learner-level data to better understand needs and address inequity.

- Develop context-specific and comparable data collection, data analysis and data storage protocols
- Collect data on educational infrastructure, enrollment and the number and geographic distribution of teachers and other members of the education workforce
- Act on this data to ensure resources are targeted to the most marginalised students, teachers, and schools
- Establish effective communication channels with and among the education workforce — education leadership, teachers, caregivers, learning teams — to coordinate education responses

Know thy...system.

Ask 2. Enhance teacher and workforce development

Enhance the quality, reach, and flexibility of school-based professional development for teachers focusing on student learning, including a wide range of holistic skills, and drawing on appropriate and cost-effective technology.

- Promote effective means of professional development: regularly scheduled school-based professional development for school-centered learning teams (teachers, parents, community workers)
- Professional development needs to focus on effective teaching practices for improved, active student learning and to utilise technology for coordination and communication
- Act on school-level data (Ask 1) to ensure teacher education programs reach teachers in the most marginalised communities

Get every child a teacher.

Ask 3. Promote inclusion and equity of learning outcomes

Ensure that every child can learn effectively — particularly those marginalised by poverty, gender, language, disability, or displacement — using appropriate learning and teaching resources, drawing on suitable technology where it offers value-for-money.

- National governments to use open curricular content and to ensure that there will be low- or no-cost ways for teachers, parents, and students to access content digitally, offline, through radio, through television, or in print
- Co-create mechanisms to share openly licensed, printable and editable content for the core curriculum including teacher guides, structured lesson plans, textbooks, workbooks, teacher professional development materials, and other multimodal resources in accessible, user-friendly formats and local languages, and targeted by learner level, for use inside and outside of the classroom

Get every child a book.

Breakout Groups

Breakout Groups (1)

Date Systems

What **big ideas** might drive forward the expansion of data systems?

Teacher & Workforce professional development

What **big ideas** might drive forward enhanced teacher and workforce development?

Inclusion and equity of learning outcomes

What **big ideas** might promote inclusion and equity of learning outcomes?

Breakout groups: (2) Mural

The discussions in the breakout rooms will be supported by an external facilitator taking notes directly into a digital collaborative tool called Mural.

Participants are also given the option to directly add notes into Mural if they want. No need to download; enter as a 'visitor'

Mural is very easy to use - add sticky notes by double clicking on the Mural, double-click on sticky notes to add/edit text or use the toolbar on the left side.

The facilitator will share the Mural link in the breakout group chat